

Original Research

The Role and Impact of Corruption in the Effect of Women's Political Empowerment on Human Development in Iran

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Abstract

Women's Political Empowerment is one of the key factors influencing human development; however, in the presence of political corruption, it may exert varying effects on human development. Accordingly, this study aimed to investigate the role and impact of corruption in the relationship between women's political empowerment and human development in Iran. This descriptive-analytical and applied study was conducted at the national level for Iran using the Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares econometric method. The annual time-series data extracted for the period 1990–2023 from databases of the World Bank, United Nations, Varieties of Democracy Institute, and Transparency International. Model estimations and required tests were performed using EViews 13 software. The findings indicated that the Women's Political Empowerment index had a positive and significant effect on the human development index in Iran across all three models. However, the interaction term between the political corruption index and the women's political empowerment index exhibited a negative and significant effect on human development. Gross Domestic Product, democracy index, and government expenditures had positive effects on human development in Iran. Increasing Women's Political Empowerment leads to enhanced human development in Iran, whereas rising political corruption diminishes the positive impact of women's Political Empowerment on human development. Thus, political corruption emerges as a significant barrier to women's political participation in Iran. Policies aimed at reducing political corruption to enhance women's political empowerment and human development are recommended. Effective anti-corruption measures include stricter regulations and penalties for corrupt activities, improved government transparency and accountability, and substantial investment in human development programs.

Keywords: Corruption, democracy, human development, Women's Political Empowerment.

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Introduction

Human development plays a fundamental role in the sustainable growth and development of societies, although this concept extends beyond mere education, skills, and individual experiences that contribute to economic efficiency and growth (Triatmanto & Bawono, 2023). Human development is a multidimensional and composite concept that, in addition to economic growth, focuses on other aspects of life, such as education, health, and improved living standards (United Nations Development Programme, 2025). The Human Development Index (HDI) is the geometric mean of indices for income, education, and life expectancy, serving as a standard measure for evaluating societal development and welfare (United Nations Development Programme, 2025).

In recent decades, identifying factors influencing human development has drawn researchers' and social activists' attention to institutional and social determinants, including Women's Political Empowerment (WPE) and governance quality through corruption reduction (Balasubramanian, Ibanez, Khan, & Sahoo, 2024; Mechkova, Dahlum, & Petrarca, 2022; Pham, 2025). Achieving gender equality and WPE is one of the Sustainable Development Goals and Millennium Development Goals of the United Nations, representing not only a means to enhance women's welfare but also an ethical imperative (Hornset & de Soysa, 2022). WPE generally encompasses their participation in public decision-making, civil society, and representation in legislative and executive branches (Mechkova et al., 2022). The Varieties of Democracy (V-Dem) Institute defines WPE as the process of enhancing women's capacity, leading to greater choice, agency, and participation in decision-making (V-Dem Institute, 2025). This empowerment not only increases women's life satisfaction and self-esteem (Hossain, Asadullah, & Kambhampati, 2019) but also promotes efficient allocation of public resources and human development (Desai, Chen, Reddy, & McLaughlin, 2022).

WPE can influence human development through multiple channels, such as affecting health and education expenditures (Azoa Balengla, Keneck-Massil, & Mondjeli Mwa Ndjokou, 2025; Desai et al., 2022; Hornset & de Soysa, 2022; Rustagi & Akter, 2022), improving good governance and reducing corruption (Azoa Balengla et al., 2025; Hornset & de Soysa, 2022; Mechkova et al., 2022), and addressing gender-related factors (Funk, Gathmann, Fumagalli, & Pijoan-Mas, 2015; Liu, Geng, Ye, & Zhou, 2019; Lv & Deng, 2019). Empirical studies have also demonstrated that WPE impacts human development by enhancing production, education, and health—the core components of human development. For instance, Ngono et al. (2021) found this effect in sub-Saharan African countries over 1981–2017 (Ngono, 2021), while Hortas-Rico and Rios (2023) showed that WPE reduces income inequality across 142 countries during 1990–2019 (Hortas-Rico & Rios, 2023). Mechkova et al. (2022) reported a positive impact on child health in 180 countries from 1990–2014 (Mechkova et al., 2022). Additionally, Azoa Balengla et al. (2025) indicated that WPE and its sub-indices negatively affect malnutrition prevalence in developing countries.

Although WPE directly influences societal welfare and development, women in many countries remain deprived of their rights to active participation in economic, social, and political spheres (Hornset & de Soysa, 2022). Notably, women's political presence may sometimes serve to legitimize male-dominated policies and appease female voters

(Nistotskaya & Stensöta, 2018; Valdini, 2019). In such contexts, women's involvement in political institutions can legitimize patriarchal policies, weaken women's political position, and ultimately reduce human development (Clayton, O'Brien, & Piscopo, 2019). Therefore, examining the impact of WPE on human development in Iran is of great importance.

Corruption reduction is another key institutional factor affecting human development. Over the past two decades, corruption's economic impact has become a critical issue, as it represents a major obstacle to human development (Hardi, Saputra, Hadiyani, Maulana, & Idroes, 2023). Corruption is not only a national but also a global phenomenon, evidenced by the World Bank's "Anti-Corruption Strategy," the United Nations Convention Against Corruption, and the OECD Convention (Pham, 2025). Corruption involves actions performed with the intent of personal gain through misuse of organizational authority, conflicting with organizational responsibilities and commitments (Triatmanto & Bawono, 2023). Reducing corruption plays a vital role in organizational efficiency, economic stability, legal systems, education, health, environmental protection, and creating a favorable business environment, among other areas (Stylianou, Nasir, & Waqas, 2023), directly contributing to development.

Theories on corruption and its impact on human development vary. Some argue that corruption can support governments in promoting economic growth and improving human development, at least in the short term (Emadzadeh & Tibash, 2023; Urbina & Rodríguez, 2021), while many contend it has destructive long-term effects on economic growth (Emadzadeh & Tibash, 2023; Emara, 2020; Pham, 2025). Studies also differ on whether corruption's impact is direct or indirect through macroeconomic variables (Emara, 2020; Shokouhifard, Aleemran, Mehrgan, & Rahimzadeh, 2020). Thus, corruption remains a primary challenge to achieving economic and human development.

Moreover, the interaction between corruption and WPE -and vice versa- leads to varying effects on human development across countries. WPE, by increasing women's leadership and political roles, promotes transparent governance, reduces corruption, enhances democracy, and improves resource management (Esarey & Schwindt-Bayer, 2019; Rios, Beltrán-Esteve, Gianmoena, Peiró-Palomino, & Picazo-Tadeo, 2023), serving as an anti-corruption tool since women in political positions are less prone to corruption (Salamon, 2025). This directly improves the HDI. Conversely, corruption weakens women's empowerment by restricting their economic, social, and political opportunities, potentially reducing human development (Mechkova et al., 2022). This bidirectional interaction can directly influence increases or decreases in human development levels.

The examination of women's political participation in Iran reveals that their share in the parliament has remained significantly low compared to men. Over the past 12 parliamentary terms, women's representation has consistently been below 6 percent. The highest level of participation occurred in the tenth parliament, at 5.8 percent, followed by the eleventh parliament at 5.4 percent and the twelfth parliament at 4.8 percent (Sangi, 2022). Concurrently, evidence indicates that political corruption in Iran has exhibited an increasing trend over recent decades (V-Dem Institute, 2025). Furthermore, there are documented instances of 'window-dressing' and strict 'party discipline' imposed on

women in Iranian politics (Sangi, 2022). Consequently, a fundamental question arises: Does the presence of political corruption in Iran contribute to a reduction in WPE, and thereby lead to a decline in the Human Development Index (HDI)? In light of these observations, investigating the impact of corruption, WPE, and their interaction on HDI in Iran is of considerable importance.

Given the importance of WPE and corruption on human development, as well as their interactive effects, this study aimed to investigate the role of corruption in the relationship between WPE and human development in Iran. It seeks to answer the following questions: What are the impacts of increasing WPE and corruption on human development in Iran? Does rising corruption diminish the effect of WPE on human development in Iran? The distinctive feature of this study is its examination of WPE and its interactions with various corruption indices in influencing the human development index. The subsequent sections present the theoretical framework, literature review, methodology, findings, discussion, and conclusion.

Theoretical Framework

Concept of Women's Political Empowerment

Women's political empowerment (WPE) is defined as the process of enhancing women's capacity, leading to greater choice, agency, and participation in decision-making. This definition encompasses three key dimensions: (1) choice, (2) agency, and (3) participation (V-Dem Institute, 2025). For the choice dimension, the Women's Civil Liberties (WCL) index is used, emphasizing women's ability to make choices in various life domains. This index is closely linked to human rights-based legal frameworks and prevailing informal cultures. For the agency dimension, the Women's Civil Society Participation (WCSP) index is employed, focusing on women's ability to act as agents of change through free participation in public discourse. For the participation dimension, the Women's Political Participation (WPP) index is applied, measuring women's involvement in political decision-making in both executive and legislative branches.

To quantify WPE, the WPE Index provided by the V-Dem Institute is utilized (V-Dem Institute, 2025). This index is the average of the three sub-indices: women's civil liberties, civil society participation, and political participation. Its values range from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating greater WPE.

Relationship between Women's Political Empowerment and Development

The theory that WPE leads to development rests on the assumption that men and women have different policy preferences (Funk et al., 2015). These differing preferences stem from gender socialization theory, shaped by life experiences in society rather than inherent biological differences (Mechkova et al., 2022). Gender socialization hypothesis suggests that women are kinder, more cooperative, and compassionate than men, leading to altruistic behaviors toward individuals and society (Liu et al., 2019), which results in policies that enhance human development.

Additionally, according to ecofeminism theory, differences between men and women arise from historical structures, cultural traditions, and patriarchal systems that assign men responsibility for political and economic affairs and women for health, nutrition, and household care programs (Lv & Deng, 2019). This theory posits lower political participation among women. It is reflected in women's policy preferences, as they tend to advocate for social policies related to children, nutrition, and women's rights (Clayton et al., 2019). Numerous studies show that women in political participation favor policies increasing maternal and child health, health expenditures, and child nutrition improvement (Besnier, 2023; Kellard, Makhlof, Sarkisyan, & Vinogradov, 2024; Mechkova & Carlitz, 2020; Rustagi & Akter, 2022).

Relationship between Corruption and Development

Corruption may be defined as the abuse of public office for private gain, such as when officials accept or solicit bribes, or when private institutions pay to influence policies or regulations for greater profit (Emadzadeh & Tibash, 2023; Emara, 2020). Corruption can affect human development both directly and indirectly (Shokouhifard et al., 2020). Its indirect effect occurs through reduced economic growth, leading to lower education and health spending (Emara, 2020). This reduction in social expenditures results in inequalities in access to education and health, ultimately causing income inequality and reduced human development (Shokouhifard et al., 2020).

Directly, corruption disrupts investment in human capital through four mechanisms. First, it weakens the tax system, leading to tax evasion and improper exemptions, reducing public resources for services like education and health. Second, it increases government operational costs, diminishing resources for other uses, including human capital formation. Third, it alters the composition of government expenditures, reducing spending on education and health (Desai et al., 2022). Fourth, it decreases the share of expenditures allocated to operations and maintenance, as such costs offer fewer rent-seeking opportunities compared to high-maintenance projects that enable bribe-taking (Shokouhifard et al., 2020). Corruption also distorts public resource allocation by shifting investments from infrastructure to concentrated capital projects, where equipment purchases provide more bribery opportunities (Emadzadeh & Tibash, 2023).

In the literature on corruption, two distinct approaches exist regarding its impact on development. The first is the "sand the wheels" hypothesis, which posits that corruption reduces efficiency. Proponents of this view argue that corruption leads to suboptimal resource allocation, diminished economic and human investment, and, consequently, lower economic growth and development (Shokouhifard et al., 2020). The mechanisms underlying these effects were outlined earlier.

In contrast, the second approach, the "grease the wheels" hypothesis, contends that corruption can enhance efficiency, at least in the short term. Advocates of this perspective maintain that corruption facilitates economic growth and development by circumventing burdensome laws and regulations, thereby promoting trade, investment, and overall economic activity (Shokouhifard et al., 2020). Furthermore, under conditions of overly rigid and cumbersome regulations, corruption may improve efficiency by enabling private sector access to production without excessive governmental restrictions (Urbina

& Rodríguez, 2021). Examples supporting the "grease the wheels" theory include the following: (1) bribery clears market obstacles; (2) bribery serves as an incentive reward for bureaucrats; and (3) bribery reduces costs (Sameti, Ranjbar, & Mohseni, 2012). A positive association between corruption and human development may also arise for other reasons. First, anti-corruption reforms can generate economic instability and disrupt public services and infrastructure. Second, such reforms may stem from the adoption of stricter policies, which could result in the closure of productive enterprises and higher unemployment. Third, combating and reducing corruption requires financial resources; in the presence of budgetary constraints, these funds are often reallocated from other sectors. If resources are diverted from foundational areas, particularly health and education, it can lead to a decline in human development (Pham, 2025).

Relationship between Women's Political Empowerment and Corruption Levels

Three main approaches exist in the literature on WPE and corruption: (1) gender differences hypothesis, (2) institutional (liberal-democratic) hypothesis, and (3) opportunity structures (Abdoullaye, 2025). The first posits that gender differences reduce corruption, as women are seen as kinder, more compassionate, risk-averse, law-abiding, and society-oriented (Buser, Grimalda, Putterman, & van der Weele, 2020; Liu et al., 2019), prioritizing public welfare over corruption (Atal & SenGupta, 2025). The second argues that liberal democracies, with checks and balances, transparency, accountability, and corruption controls, reduce opportunities for corruption (Abdoullaye, 2025). The third suggests that the gender-corruption link arises because women are excluded from sensitive decision-making positions or deliberately kept away (Paxton, Hughes, & Barnes, 2020).

Interactive Effects of Women's Political Empowerment and Corruption Levels on Human Development

As noted earlier, WPE represents one of the key factors influencing development, affecting development levels through various channels. Recent studies have also examined this relationship (Hornset & de Soysa, 2022; Hortas-Rico & Rios, 2023; Ngono, 2021). However, this relationship can be moderated by other factors. Research has shown that simply increasing women's presence in politics does not automatically advance development goals; rather, institutional factors such as corruption are highly significant (Clayton & Zetterberg, 2021; Donno & Kreft, 2019; Nistotskaya & Stensöta, 2018; Valdini, 2019).

The effect of corruption on the relationship between WPE and the Human HDI can be conceptualized as follows: In societies with high levels of corruption, the positive impact of WPE on development is attenuated. Conversely, in societies with low corruption, the beneficial effect of WPE on development is strengthened (Mechkova et al., 2022). In other words, corruption can weaken WPE, thereby reducing the level of HDI. In such cases, the interaction of corruption and WPE on HDI is smaller than the direct effect of WPE on HDI. If corruption is sufficiently high to neutralize the positive effect of WPE on HDI, the interaction term would exhibit a negative relationship with HDI. In contrast, when corruption is low or decreasing, the interaction of corruption and WPE on HDI would exceed the isolated effect of WPE.

One primary reason why corruption leads to the weakening of both WPE and HDI is "window-dressing" of women in politics (Clayton & Zetterberg, 2021; Donno & Kreft, 2019; Nistotskaya & Stensöta, 2018). This refers to situations in which political parties or influential groups attempt to increase the number of women in political positions while retaining actual control over decision-making processes. The introduction of gender quotas is one common means of achieving this goal. For example, Franceschet and Piscopo (2008) showed in the case of Argentina that women's selection for political office often relied on kinship ties and intra-party favoritism. Party leaders supported female relatives in elections to meet quota requirements, while continuing to dominate political decision-making thereafter (Franceschet & Piscopo, 2008). Similarly, Nistotskaya and Stensöta (2018) demonstrated in Russia that the increased presence of women in parliament had a populist character, with women's political decisions remaining heavily influenced by the ruling authorities. Another key mechanism is party discipline (Clayton & Zetterberg, 2021). Party discipline can influence this relationship for two main reasons. First, political parties tend to provide greater support to women than to men because women generally have fewer independent resources for attracting voters and maintaining popular backing; as a result, women become more dependent on their parties. Second, due to prevailing gender norms, women are less likely to oppose party policies (Clayton & Zetterberg, 2021). These gender norms are rooted in gender socialization theory, which holds that women are perceived as kinder, more compassionate, and more peace-oriented (Buser et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2019). Clayton and Zetterberg (2021) found that female parliamentarians in African countries who adhere to party discipline exhibit lower levels of opposition to patriarchal policies and legislation.

Literature Review

The body of research on the impact of corruption on human development is particularly rich, with selected studies summarized here. Emara (2025), using an autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model for Egypt over 1995–2018, found that corruption has a negative and significant effect on human development in both the short and long term. Per capita gross domestic product and government expenditures exert positive and significant effects on human development in both periods. Pham (2025), employing pooled OLS, fixed effects, and random effects models for Vietnam over 2012–2022, showed that the corruption perception index has a negative and significant impact on human development in both the short and long term. Hardi et al. (2023), using fully modified ordinary least squares (FMOLS) and dynamic ordinary least squares (DOLS) models for Indonesia, found no direct significant effect of corruption on human development, nor any causal relationship between the two. However, government expenditures and public debt moderate the impact of corruption on human development. Emadzadeh and Tibash (2023), using panel data models for Islamic countries, demonstrated that corruption reduces the human development index in the long term but has a positive effect in the short term. Urbina (2021), applying a Bayesian panel vector autoregression model for Latin American and Nordic countries, found that corruption's effect on economic growth varies—positive in some Latin American countries and negative in others—but overall, corruption negatively impacts human development across all countries in both regions. Triatmanto and Bawono (2023) for Indonesia using a vector error correction model over 1996–2021, Murshed and Mredula (2018) with panel data for Asian, African, and Latin American countries over 2000–2015, and Barros, Baggio,

Stege, and Hilgemberg (2019) for Brazil all demonstrated that corruption negatively affects human development.

A group of studies has also examined the impact of WPE on welfare and economic development. Azoa Balengla et al. (2025) demonstrated that WPE and all its sub-indices have a negative effect on the prevalence of malnutrition in developing countries. This effect is further strengthened through good governance, health expenditures, and education spending. Kellard et al. (2024) analyzed 134 countries over the period 1950–2018 and found that women's civil, political, and economic empowerment reduces child mortality in high-income countries, with a substantially greater impact in low- and middle-income countries. Balasubramanian et al. (2024), through a meta-analysis of low- and middle-income countries, showed that women's empowerment has a strong positive effect on human development. They also emphasized the critical role of social norms in achieving sustainable development. Support for agricultural activities and entrepreneurship, expanded financial access, and greater economic participation of female labor contribute to women's empowerment. Hornset and de Soysa (2022), using fixed-effects ordinary least squares regressions for MENA countries, found that WPE is positively associated with human capital. It positively affects access to education and health, as well as secondary school completion, while negatively impacting child mortality rates. Democracy and institutional quality play significant roles in mediating these effects. Hortas-Rico and Rios (2023) examined 142 countries over the period 1990–2019 and demonstrated that WPE, gross domestic product, government expenditures, democracy, education, and financial development negatively affect income inequality, whereas unemployment and urbanization positively influence income inequality. Mechkova et al. (2022), investigating good governance, gender inequality, and human development across 180 countries from 1990–2014, found that increased WPE positively affects human development, provided that good governance is achieved through reduced corruption. Ngono et al. (2021) showed for sub-Saharan African countries over 1981–2017 that women's economic, political, and social empowerment can reduce income inequality, with the effect being stronger when accompanied by increased female self-employment. Besnier (2023) revealed that the WPE index is directly associated with improved nutrition and vaccination rates and negatively correlated with child mortality. The impact on stunting is notably stronger in middle-income countries, while the effect on vaccination is more pronounced in low-income countries. Rustagi and Akter (2022), for 162 countries over 1990–2022, and Doku, Bhutta, and Neupane (2020), for low- and middle-income countries, demonstrated that women's political participation has a significant negative effect on infant mortality rates. Furthermore, women's political representation influences child health outcomes through health expenditures, female labor force participation, and adolescent fertility rates (Doku et al., 2020; Rustagi & Akter, 2022).

The literature review reveals that one group of studies has examined the impact of corruption on human development, while another group has focused on the effects of WPE on human development. However, only a limited number of studies have investigated the interactive effects of corruption and WPE on outcomes such as climate change, health status, and income inequality. Given this research gap, the present study examines the interaction effects of corruption and WPE on human development in Iran.

Methodology

This study is descriptive-analytical and applied that conducted at the national level for Iran using the Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (DOLS) econometric method. The required data consist of annual time-series, extracted for the period 1990–2023 from databases of the World Bank, United Nations, Varieties of Democracy (V-Dem) Institute, and Transparency International. Model estimations and necessary tests were performed using EViews 13 software. To examine the effects of corruption and WPE on human development, based on the theoretical framework and prior studies, Hornset & de Soysa, 2022; Mechkova et al., 2022; Hardi et al., 2023; Pham, 2025, the following conceptual model was developed. Given that one objective of this study is to investigate the impact of corruption (political and executive) on human development through WPE, interaction terms between the corruption indices and the WPE index were included

$$\text{Equation 1: } HDI = f(WPE, CORRUPTION, WPE \times CORRUPTION, CONTROLE)$$

HDI: Human Development Index

WPE: Women's Political Empowerment

Corruption: the level of corruption. In this study, two indices were used: Political Corruption Index (PCI) and Executive Corruption Index (ECI), based on V-Dem data

Control variables: Selected based on studies by Emara (2020), Hardi et al. (2023), Pham (2025), Azoa Balengla et al. (2025), Ngono (2021), and Mechkova et al. (2022). Definitions and abbreviations are provided below. The estimable models are specified as follows:

$$\text{Equation 2: } HDI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 WPE + \beta_2 PCI + \beta_3 WPPC + \beta_4 GDP + \beta_5 DEM + \beta_6 INF + \beta_7 EXP + \varepsilon$$

$$\text{Equation 3: } HDI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 WPE + \beta_2 ECI + \beta_3 WPEC + \beta_4 GDP + \beta_5 DEM + \beta_6 INF + \beta_7 EXP + \varepsilon$$

$$\text{Equation 4: } HDI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 WPE + \beta_2 CPI + \beta_3 WPCP + \beta_4 GDP + \beta_5 DEM + \beta_6 INF + \beta_7 EXP + \varepsilon$$

HDI: Human Development Index

WPE: Women's Political Empowerment

PCI: Political Corruption Index

WPPC: Interaction term between WPE and PCI.

GDP: Gross Domestic Product Per capita

DEM: Democracy Index

INF: Inflation rate

EXP: Government expenditures on education and health as a percentage of GDP.

ECI: Executive Corruption Index

WPEC: Interaction term between WPE and ECI.

CPI: Corruption Perceptions Index. (rescaled to 0–100, where higher values indicate greater corruption).

WPCP: Interaction term between WPE and CPI

Equation 4 was specified to assess the robustness and stability of equation 2 and 3. In this model, corruption is measured using the Corruption Perception Index (CPI). This index Published by Transparency International, is scored from 0 to 100, with higher values indicating lower perceived corruption. To ensure consistency with other corruption measures in this study and to facilitate interpretation, we reversed the scale as follows: $CPI = 100 - \text{original CPI}$. Higher scores denote greater corruption. Additionally, the interaction term between WPE and CPI was included to examine corruption's effect through WPE. Various methods exist for estimating time-series models, but prior to estimation, the stationary of variables must be examined. If variables are stationary, their levels can be used for coefficient estimation. However, if they are non-stationary at levels, level estimation is valid only if a long-run cointegration relationship is confirmed (Shahraki, 2019). Stationary was tested using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) unit root tests. The null hypothesis assumes non-stationary. If the calculated test statistic exceeds the critical value at the relevant significance level, the null is rejected, indicating stationary (Shahraki & Ghaderi, 2021). Cointegration among variables was assessed using the Johansen method, which employs Trace and Maximum Eigenvalue tests to determine the number of cointegrating vectors. Given the stationary results and confirmed cointegration, the Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (DOLS) method was employed to estimate the model coefficients. This approach yields highly consistent estimators that are asymptotically unbiased, with normally distributed error terms, lower root mean squared errors, and no correlation between errors and independent variables. It effectively addresses endogeneity and autocorrelation issues (Shahraki, 2019).

Post-estimation diagnostic and stability tests following the application of the DOLS method are essential to ensure the validity of the results. In this study, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test was used for stationarity, the Jarque-Bera test for the normality of the residuals, the Hansen Parameter Instability test for coefficient stability, and the Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) test for examining multicollinearity. The null hypothesis in the Jarque-Bera test is the normality of the residuals, and in the Hansen Parameter Instability test it is the stability of the coefficients (No parameter instability). If VIF is less than 10, multicollinearity is low; if it is between 10 and 20, it is moderate; and if it is greater than 20, it is high.

Results

Descriptive statistics revealed a mild upward trend in the HDI over the study period. The HDI value was 0.63 in 1990, rising to 0.79 in 2023, with a mean of 0.74. The WPE index exhibited a similar mild upward trend, with a mean of 0.31. The corruption indices PCI and ECI displayed coordinated increasing trends, with ECI consistently lower than PCI throughout the period. Additional descriptive statistics for the model variables are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of variables

	Mean	Maximum	Minimum	Skewness	Kurtosis	Probability (Jarque-Bera)
HDI	0.740	0.799	0.626	-0.609	2.002	0.172
WPE	0.319	0.371	0.241	-1.013	2.734	0.152
PCI	0.674	0.796	0.516	-0.566	1.796	0.145
WPPC	0.216	0.281	0.153	-0.078	1.325	0.135
ECI	0.622	0.760	0.471	-0.960	2.407	0.157
WPEC	0.198	0.253	0.153	-0.018	1.294	0.127
CPI	73.850	85.000	70.000	0.206	2.946	0.181
WPCP	23.538	27.370	17.581	-1.027	2.686	0.147
GDP	4539.797	5667.526	3222.201	-0.334	1.555	0.166
DEM	0.124	0.163	0.078	-0.014	3.098	0.993
INF	22.140	49.656	7.245	0.818	2.609	0.134
EXP	8.982	11.359	7.254	0.509	2.976	0.480

To examine the stationarity of the variables, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests were employed, with results presented in Table 2. The findings indicated that all variables exhibited a unit root at levels and became stationary after first differencing. In other words, all variables were integrated of order one, I (1).

Table 2: Results of unit root tests

	Augmented Dickey-Fuller test		Phillips-Perron test		Result
	t-Statistic	Prob	t-Statistic	Prob	
D HDI	-3.10	0.03	-3.17	0.03	Stationary
D WPE	-4.52	0.001	-4.51	0.003	Stationary
PCI D	-5.54	0.0001	-5.53	0.0001	Stationary
D WPPC	-6.33	0.0001	-6.33	0.0001	Stationary
D ECI	-5.30	0.000	-5.31	0.000	Stationary
D WPEC	-6.22	0.000	-6.24	0.000	Stationary
D CPI	-5.42	0.000	-5.62	0.000	Stationary
D WPCP	-5.23	0.0001	-5.71	0.0001	Stationary
D GDP	-4.97	0.001	-4.94	0.001	Stationary
D DEM	-3.30	0.02	-3.31	0.03	Stationary
D INF	-5.89	0.0002	-7.17	0.000	Stationary
D EXP	-4.11	0.003	-4.14	0.003	Stationary

D=1'st difference

To examine the existence of cointegration among the variables in the models, the Johansen cointegration test was employed. The results of this test, based on both the Trace statistic and Maximum Eigenvalue statistic, are reported for each model in the results tables (in the final row). The results showed that there is at least one cointegrating relationship among the model variables. Therefore, with confidence, the DOLS method can be used to estimate the models.

To estimate Equation (2), Models 1 to 4 were estimated, and the results are presented in Table 3. Model 1 included only the main study variables (without control variables), while Models 2 to 4 incorporated the control variables. Stability and diagnostic tests were performed for all models, with results reported at the bottom of each model's column. The results of Model 1 indicated that, despite confirmation of cointegration (Johansen Cointegration Test) and coefficient stability (Hansen Parameter Instability Test), severe multicollinearity was detected based on the Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) test. To address multicollinearity, control variables were included, and Model 2 was estimated. The results of Model 2 showed that while multicollinearity was reduced and the long-run relationship was confirmed, severe multicollinearity persisted, potentially biasing the estimates. At this stage, PCI and WPPC were identified as the variables exhibiting high multicollinearity. In Model 3, PCI, and in Model 4, WPPC was excluded from the baseline specification. Diagnostic and stability tests for Models 3 and 4 confirmed that multicollinearity had decreased to an acceptable level, the long-run relationship was supported, and coefficient stability was established. Thus, the coefficients from these models are reliable. The results of Model 3 revealed that WPE and the control variables GDP, DEM, and INF exert positive and significant effects on HDI in Iran, whereas WPPC has a negative and significant effect. In other words, WPE contributes to higher HDI in Iran, but political corruption (WPPC) attenuates this positive impact. The results of Model 4 indicated that WPE and the control variables GDP and EXP have positive and significant effects, while PCI exerts a negative and significant effect on the HDI.

Table 3: Results of the Impact of Women's Political Empowerment and Political Corruption on Human Development (Equation 2)

Variable	Model (1)	Model (2)	Model (3)	Model (4)
WPE	5.288***	4.916***	0.563*	0.273*
PCI	2.519***	2.178**		-0.146**
WPPC	-6.799***	-6.70***	-0.409*	
GDP		3.32E-05**	6.59E-05**	6.91E-05**
DEM		0.691**	0.286*	0.27963
INF		0.0003***	8.11E-05*	6.74E-05
EXP		0.0135***	0.004	0.003*
C	-1.182	-0.992***	0.367*	0.458**
Control	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
R-squared	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.99
Jarque-Bera Probability	0.92	0.53	0.47	0.65
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test – Probability	0.028	0.001	0.005	0.032
Hansen Parameter Instability	>0.2	>0.2	>0.2	>0.2

Variance Inflation Factors (VIF)		Very High	High	Low	Low
Johansen Cointegrating Test	Trace Test	At most 1	At most 4	At most 1	At most 1
	Max-Eigenvalue Test	At most 1	At most 3	At most 1	At most 1

* Significance at 10%., ** Significance at 5%., *** Significance at 1%.

To estimate Equation (3), Models 5 through 8 were estimated, with results presented in Table 4. Model 5 included only the core variables WPE, ECI, and their interaction term (WPEC). Although cointegration and coefficient stability were confirmed, severe multicollinearity was detected in this specification. Control variables were therefore added, and Model 6 was estimated. In Model 6, both ECI and WPEC displayed negative and statistically significant effects on HDI; however, multicollinearity remained substantial. To resolve this issue, ECI was removed in Model 7 and WPEC was removed in Model 8. Both specifications exhibited acceptable levels of multicollinearity. The results of Model 7 indicate that WPE, GDP, and INF exert positive and statistically significant effects on HDI, whereas WPEC has a negative and significant effect. The results of Model 8 show that WPE, GDP, DEM, and EXP have positive and significant effects on HDI, while ECI exerts a negative and significant effect on the HDI in Iran. Taken together, the findings reported in Table 4 reveal that WPE has a positive and statistically significant impact on HDI in Iran, whereas ECI exerts a negative and significant impact. Moreover, the presence of ECI substantially attenuates the positive effect of WPE on HDI in Iran.

Table 4: Results of the Impact of Women's Political Empowerment and Executive Corruption on Human Development (Equation 3)

Variable	Model (5)	Model (6)	Model (7)	Model (8)
WPE	10.505**	0.264	0.486*	0.268**
ECI	4.857**	-0.118*		-0.114**
WPEC	-14.188**	-0.126*	-0.322*	
GDP		6.85E-05***	6.12E-05***	6.19E-05***
DEM		0.347**	0.243	0.279*
INF		5.69E-05	0.0001*	
EXP		0.004**		0.003*
C	-2.805*	0.467	0.393***	0.472***
Control	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
R-squared	0.98	0.98	0.99	0.98
Jarque-Bera Probability	0.85	0.83	0.72	0.42
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test – Probability	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.01
Hansen Parameter Instability	>0.2	>0.2	>0.2	>0.2

Variance Inflation Factors (VIF)		Very High	High	Medium	Medium
Johansen Cointegrating Test	Trace Test	At most 1	At most 4	At most 1	At most 1
	Max-Eigenvalue Test	At most 1	At most 3	At most 1	At most 1

* Significance at 10%., ** Significance at 5%., *** Significance at 1%.

To ensure the robustness of the results obtained from Equations (2) and (3), Equation (3) was specified. In this equation, the CPI was employed as the measure of corruption. The CPI is scaled from 0 to 100, where a higher score indicates greater corruption. The estimation results for Equation (4), using Models 9 through 12, are presented in Table 5. Models 9 and 10 exhibited severe multicollinearity. To address this issue, in Models 11 and 12, the variables CPI and WPCP were sequentially excluded from the estimation, respectively. The results of stability and diagnostic tests confirmed the cointegration, moderate multicollinearity, and coefficient stability in these two models. The error terms were also found to be normally distributed and stationary. Models (11) and (12) revealed that the variables WPE, GDP, DEM, INF, and EXP exerted positive and statistically significant effects on HDI, whereas WPCP had a negative and significant impact. However, CPI did not exhibit a statistically significant effect.

Table 5: Results of the Impact of Women’s Political Empowerment and Corruption (CPI) on Human Development (Equation 4)

Variable	Model (9)	Model (10)	Model (11)	Model (12)	
WPE	19.568	42.18***	0.449***	-0.147	
CPI	0.1342	-0.186***		-0.0001	
WPCP	-0.399	0.570**	-0.0003*		
GDP		8.86E-05***	5.92E-05***	8.54E-05***	
DEM		1.380***		0.972**	
INF		0.003*		0.0007**	
EXP		0.012**	3.88E-03*		
C	-9.253	13.85**	3.62E-01***	0.280***	
Control	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	
R-squared	0.93	0.98	0.99	0.99	
Jarque-Bera Probability	0.21	0.72	0.35	0.49	
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test – Probability	0.11	0.000	0.002	0.0001	
Hansen Parameter Instability	>0.2	>0.2	>0.2	>0.2	
Variance Inflation Factors (VIF)	Very High	Very High	Medium	Medium	
Johansen Cointegrating Test	Trace Test	At most 1	At most 4	At most 2	At most 3
	Max-Eigenvalue Test	At most 1	At most 4	At most 2	At most 3

* Significance at 10%., ** Significance at 5%., *** Significance at 1%.

Furthermore, to enhance the robustness of the results obtained using the DOLS method, Models 13 through 16 were employed, with the results presented in Table (6). These models were estimated based on the FMOLS method. The outcomes of the stability and diagnostic tests indicated confirmation of cointegration, coefficient stability, and the absence of bias in the results. In these models, WPE exerted a positive effect, while the interactive effects of WPPC and WPEC had negative impacts on HDI in Iran. These findings were consistent with the results from the DOLS method. The corruption indices PCI and ECI did not exhibit statistically significant effects.

Table 6: Results of the Impact of Women’s Political Empowerment and Corruption Index on Human Development (FMOLS Method)

Variable	Model (13)	Model (14)	Model (15)	Model (16)
WPE	0.369***	0.326***	0.361***	0.326**
PCI		-0.023		
WPPC	-0.095*			
ECI				-0.019
WPEC			-0.065*	
GDP	5.45E-05***	5.36E-05***	5.26E-05***	5.24E-05***
INF	0.0003*	0.0003*	0.0003*	0.0003*
EXP	0.0055*	0.005	0.005*	0.005
C	0.357***	0.373***	0.364**	0.376**
Control	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
R-squared	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.96
Jarque-Bera Probability	0.73	0.78	0.76	0.75
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test – Probability	0.02	0.03	0.002	0.03
Hansen Parameter Instability	>0.2	>0.2	>0.2	>0.2
Variance Inflation Factors (VIF)	Low	Low	Low	Low
Johansen Cointegrating Test	Trace Test	At most 5	At most 4	At most 4
	Max-Eigenvalue Test	At most 2	At most 2	At most 2

* Significance at 10%, ** Significance at 5%, *** Significance at 1%.

Discussion

This study investigates the role of corruption in the impact of women's political empowerment on human development in Iran. To this end, three equations were estimated using the DOLS method. Three distinct corruption indicators were employed: political corruption, executive corruption, and the Corruption Perceptions Index. The results indicate that WPE exerts a positive and statistically significant effect on the HDI across all three equations. Furthermore, robustness checks conducted using the FMOLS method confirm the consistency and validity of these findings. These findings are consistent with prior studies by Azoa Balengla et al. (2025), Kellard et al. (2024), Hornset and de Soysa (2022), and Rustagi and Akter (2022). Overall, greater WPE and increased presence of female policymakers can influence legislative decisions and, ultimately, development in

multiple ways. First, it normalizes women's participation in politics, signaling to all policymakers the need to pay greater attention to women's interests and priorities. Second, female politicians are more actively engaged in discussions related to women's rights and other gender issues compared to their male counterparts. Third, women's gendered experiences may enrich legislative debates and encourage male lawmakers to adopt approaches that better reflect women's preferences. Fourth, female lawmakers can motivate policymakers to promote shared interests through informal negotiations and bargaining (Hortas-Rico & Rios, 2023). Additionally, politically empowered women typically pursue policies that enhance social preferences and societal welfare. This mechanism is associated with greener choices and increased expenditures on education and health, as women prioritize sustainable consumption and investment in human capital to achieve long-term societal well-being (Atal & SenGupta, 2025). Therefore, based on the findings of this study, increasing women's political empowerment is recommended as a key strategy to enhance human development in Iran. In this regard, gender-specific institutional reforms are advised, including the establishment of independent women's councils and the implementation of quotas for women in political institutions.

The results also revealed that political corruption and executive corruption indices exert a negative and statistically significant impact on the Human Development Index in Iran. This finding aligns with the "sand the wheels" hypothesis, which posits that corruption acts as a major impediment to development by reducing efficiency. This result is consistent with previous studies (Emara, 2020; Urbina & Rodríguez, 2021; Murshed & Mredula, 2018; Triatmanto & Bawono, 2023). Corruption can indirectly affect human development through reduced economic growth. Reduced economic growth leads to reduced spending on education and health, and ultimately reduced human development (Emara, 2020). Directly, corruption increases economic costs, reduces productivity across various sectors, and diverts government investment from essential areas such as health and education toward non-productive sectors (Emadzadeh & Tibash, 2023; Triatmanto & Bawono, 2023).

Furthermore, corruption weakens tax and financial systems, results in inefficient resource allocation, and increases unnecessary government expenditures, all of which directly undermine human development (Shokouhifard et al., 2020; Urbina & Rodríguez, 2021). Corruption is not merely a domestic challenge but a global one. High levels of corruption also deter foreign investment by reducing competitiveness and, consequently, limiting the attraction of foreign capital (Jazuli, Idris, & Yaguma, 2022). In light of these findings, it is recommended that policies aimed at reducing corruption be adopted, including the enforcement of stricter regulations and harsher penalties for corrupt activities, as well as measures to enhance government transparency and accountability.

To investigate the role of corruption in the effect of WPE on human development, interaction terms between the corruption indices and WPE were incorporated into the models. The results showed that the interaction effects of WPE with the political corruption index (WPPC) and the executive corruption index (WPEC) are negative on HDI in both the DOLS and FMOLS methods. In other words, higher levels of political and executive corruption in Iran diminish the positive impact of WPE on HDI. This finding is consistent with Mechkova et al. (2022), who argued that in countries with low corruption levels, increases in WPE lead to improvements in HDI, whereas in high-

corruption settings, increases in WPE may result in declines in HDI, a pattern characteristic of many developing countries.

In Iran's political context, evidence of political corruption manifests through political collusion and the dominance of parties in selecting women as parliamentary representatives. Consistent with the "window-dressing" theory of women's representation, in the eleventh parliamentary term, the conservative list for Tehran included five female candidates among 30 nominees, all of whom were elected (Sangi, 2022). Moreover, in previous parliamentary, a considerable number of female representatives entered parliament through their connections with famous political figures and personalities, both causally and relatively. Additionally, women's access to parliamentary seats has overwhelmingly depended on party and political faction support (Sangi, 2022), exemplifying strong party discipline in Iran. These examples indicate that window-dressing and party discipline serve as mechanisms of political corruption in Iran, effectively constraining genuine WPE. Consequently, political corruption emerges as a significant barrier to both WPE and human development in Iran. In this regard, reducing corruption levels is recommended to strengthen WPE and, in turn, enhance human development.

Although corruption hinders WPE, anti-corruption reforms remain feasible within Iran's political and legal framework. One effective approach to reducing corruption while promoting WPE is to increase women's social capital (Sangi, 2022), which can be achieved by enhancing their self-confidence, improving access to education, and expanding economic resources. Furthermore, creating an open political environment through strengthened elections and the rule of law, along with advancing political development via the promotion of a democratic political culture, can contribute to lowering corruption and increasing women's empowerment.

The results of the study indicate that an increase in the democracy is directly associated with improvements in human development in Iran. This finding is consistent with numerous previous studies, including Haile and Niño-Zarazúa (2018), Shahraki and Ghaderi (2021b), and Hornset and de Soysa (2022). Governments suffering from legitimacy crises tend to have inefficient labor forces and weak financial markets, which lead to market failures, economic inefficiencies, and reduced development (Shahraki & Ghaderi, 2021b). Higher levels of democracy create the necessary conditions for the adequate provision of public goods and can therefore significantly influence development. Moreover, improvements in democratic quality enhance the efficiency of government expenditure, which in turn positively affects the HDI (Shahraki & Ghaderi, 2021b). WPE is also closely linked to the state of democracy (Hornset & de Soysa, 2022). For this reason, including democracy as an explanatory variable alongside WPE in the development equation was essential. Democratic institutions have a significant impact on political and civil liberties (Haile & Niño-Zarazúa, 2018), thereby creating favorable conditions for improving both WPE and HDI.

Although a bidirectional relationship between democracy and WPE is generally supported, evidence from countries such as India, Pakistan, and Argentina shows that high levels of democracy can coexist with limited women's political empowerment (Franceschet & Piscopo, 2008; Hornset & de Soysa, 2022). Nevertheless, the majority of

studies demonstrate that in democratic regimes, women's empowerment contributes to better provision of public goods and overall development (Desai et al., 2022; Dahlum, Knutsen, & Mechkova, 2022). In other words, the level of democracy serves as one of the key mechanisms through which WPE can influence human development. Accordingly, policies aimed at improving democratic quality and expanding political and civil liberties are recommended.

The results further revealed that GDP, inflation, and government expenditure exert positive and statistically significant effects on HDI in Iran. These findings are in line with a large body of existing research (Emara, 2020; Haile & Niño-Zarazúa, 2018; Mechkova et al., 2022; Pham, 2025; Shahraki & Ghaderi, 2021b). Production and government spending, particularly in education and health, contribute to human development by improving living standards, including access to basic facilities, healthcare services, and adequate nutrition. They also enhance purchasing power and raise education levels, which directly promote human development (Haile & Niño-Zarazúa, 2018; Hardi et al., 2023). Regarding the effect of inflation on economic growth and development in Iran, a non-linear relationship (both positive and negative) has been reported. Additionally, the non-linear impact of inflation on income distribution leads to differential effects on economic growth and development (Moradzadeh, Shirmehenji, & Nourahmadi, 2022; Nazari & Barzegar Davin, 2015).

This study was subject to several limitations: 1) The limited volume of data available for Iran, which somewhat restricts the application of cointegration techniques. 2) The inclusion of a large number of variables in the DOLS method, which may result in inappropriate lag selection and potential bias in the estimates. 3) The possibility of multicollinearity among variables. 4) Given the statistical insignificance of the coefficients for corruption and inflation in some models, future research should examine their short-run and long-run effects separately.

Conclusion

This study was conducted to investigate the role of corruption in the relationship between WPE and human development in Iran. The results demonstrated that the WPE index has a positive and significant effect on the human development index in Iran. Therefore, enhancing women's political empowerment is recommended to promote human development. This can be achieved through increased women's participation in politics and expanded political and civil liberties for women. Additionally, gender-specific institutional reforms, such as the implementation of quotas for women in political institutions, are advised. Political and executive corruption had a negative impact on human development. Moreover, higher levels of political and executive corruption lead to a reduction in the effect of women's political empowerment on the human development. The democracy index, production, and government expenditures also exhibited positive effects on human development. In light of the results, political corruption emerges as a significant and inhibitory factor for women's political participation and, consequently, for human development in Iran. The following policies are recommended: creating an open political environment through strengthened elections and the rule of law; promoting a democratic political culture; enforcing stricter regulations and harsher penalties for

corrupt activities; improving government transparency and accountability; and making substantial investments in human capital development programs.

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Authors' contributions

Conceptualization, Data analysis, Study design and final approval:

Conflict of interest

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